

Describing spiritual healing : the needed words and diagrams

When I observe individuals and groups involved in spiritual healing processes I have « problems » with some words :

- ASC Altered States of Consciousness
- hallucinations
- otherworld
- ritual
- shaman
- priest

In this paper I explore these different issues and make proposals for new words, new expressions, new diagrams.

This goes with new understanding.

I hope I can help researchers who are in a similar situation : observe and name facts within the realm of spiritual healing.

Naming the one who experiences hallucinations

In a paper, to have the story vivid it is important to name correctly who has the hallucinations.

Some names don't fit :

- the patient : only in a low % of cases suffering is associated with hallucinations
- the subject : subject of what, of who ?
- the individual : hallucination is associated with a sort of ubiquity i.e. being both in the real world and in the other world i.e. being somehow dividual and not individual
- the person : there are too many « personalism » and the insistence on the subjectivity of these personalisms is contradictory with the fact that there are several actors which the one who experiences hallucinations - from the healing shaman to the healing priest
- some authors name their character « Fred » or « Peter" : they are male names !

I found a solution consisting in naming the character of the stories I tell « Claude ».

Claude fits for a man - Claude Levi-Stauss

Claude fits for a woman - Claude Sarraute

Claude fits for the actor of the first burial 100 thousand years ago.

Claude may be the shaman drawing on a cave wall 40 thousand years ago.

Claude fits with the first builder of a wheeled cart 5 thousand years ago.

Claude fits with an actor of the war of Troy - the Iliad - 2800 years ago.

Claude fits with a character of the Odyssey a few hundred years after.

These many people who experience hallucinations

We were interested by a paper by Wenge Huang who describes how Gautama, in his period as an anchorite, had the experience of hallucinations.

Globally, there is a sort of « coming out ».

It's no more a shame to have hallucinations actually - if you are a lonesome sailor for example (1).

About past characters, « occidental » people can realize that Gautama had hallucinations.

Among these many people experiencing hallucinations we meet :

1. the anchorite in his remote cave
2. the man experiencing NDE
3. the lonesome sailor
4. the engineer in his deaf room
5. the shaman
6. Claude experiencing softly entheogenes - LSD, psilocybe, ayahuasca
7. Claude with virus/bacteria and fever
8. People who, in their ordinary and quiet life, are prone to hearing voices, etc.
9. People who hear certain kinds of music - binaural, etc.
10. People doing meditation with overbreathing, etc
11. and more Claude in different situations

In these palette of « games », many experiencers witness having traveled to an otherworld.

Or experiencing the projection of senses to something like an otherworld.

The otherworld is an enhanced version of the real world or a special version of the real world. It is generally peaceful.

The otherworld

Illustration : reproduction of a drawing of a bison in the Altamira cave

More and more researchers suspect that the drawings in the caves 40 thousands year ago where made by shamans as a log book of their travel to the other world.

First argument is that the scenes don't correspond to the real world of the hunters.

The usual preys have not the first role, unusual beasts are represented.

The second argument is the presence, on the walls, beside the animals, of « weird » signs.

Illustration : reproduction of signs in a cave : spiral, svastika and wavy lines

These signs have similarities with what is experienced in shamanic travel to the otherworld and in NDE experiences.

Illustration : The world, the otherworld and the ways between

In the drawing, I chose the flying fairy, the unicorn and the wyvern as symbols of characters that are met in each world - see Mike Williams books.

So the wholeworld is made of the supposed « realworld » + the otherworld.

To be complete there are also the ways from one to the other.

The tunnel to the lowerworld.

Something to climb to the upperworld - a tree, a giant beanstalk, a flying eagle, etc.

The reality of the otherworld and the « as if » attitude

The importance of the « as if » attitude was developed by Hans Vahinger.

Shall we put it simply.

« Is the otherworld inside the brain of Claude, is it outside or both ? »

For the healing practitioner this question is absolutely irrelevant.

The healer cannot put a ladder in Claude's brain !!!

The practitioner makes **as if** the other world is outside Claude's brain.

Because outside it's possible to « play » the situation that has to be improved.

Because a mind trouble has always inside factors and outside factors.

The word hallucinations is too installed in the realm of madness

It's terrible !

Reading the Wikipedia article on Auditory hallucinations shows the word « psychotic » on the fifth line !!!

The article should present first the **perfect normality** of ordinary auditory hallucinations. And then cases where hallucinations are associated with suffering.

So I create and use the word xenophany.

« xeno » refers to the otherworld **as if** the otherworld is on the other side of a frontier.

« phany » comes from the word for « shine » in indo-european language.

« shine » is not only for images but also applies to the 5 senses.

Shining sounds, shining proprioception, shining tastes, shining smells.

There is more than 5 senses : shining X sense, shining Y sense.

Xenophany is the experience of the travel to the otherworld and any other experience of something « other » « over ».

A vehicle is not an altered state of a tricycle !!!

No, I am not in a state of weird thinking !

I just use a metaphore, an analogy, a comparison : look !

A vehicle is an altered state
of a tricycle

AST

A tricycle

Before

Original wholeness is an
altered state of consciousness

ASC

Modern consciousness

After

We have two sentences based on the same process.

A tricycle is « after » 5 thousand years of vehicles.

After all the vehicles developed from the wheel carts of the Yamnaya/kurgan culture

Consciousness is a « modern » invention.

Julian Jaynes shows that there is no or few consciousness in the words of the Iliad - 2800 years ago.

Consciousness comes a long time after the realm of xenophanies, otherworld, etc.

Using the formula ASC means that the past, the « before » is an **altered state of the future**, of the « after ».

In phylogenesis, there are three steps :

- step 1 : mankind is in a wholeness made of realworld + otherworld with xenophanies to travel in between
- step 2 : about the time of the Iliad - 2800 years ago - some Claude develop a small peephole that we call « consciousness ». Julian Jaynes describes thoroughly how in that peephole we see only a very small part of reality.

Original wholeness with xenophanies cannot be an **altered state of a peephole** !!!

- step 3 : the first few Claude **teach other humans** how to make a peephole in their thinking process.

In ontogenesis, the child lives three steps :

- step 1 : the child is in a wholeness full of fantasies, of imagined friends living in imagined worlds.
- step 2 : the mirror and the adults say to the child « *You can be introspective, you can feel the difference between you and the world, you and the others !* »
- Very slowly the child develops the peephole called consciousness and names what can be seen in the peephole : the self

So consciousness always :

- comes after
- is narrower

The same as the tricycle :

- comes after
- is narrower than the span of possible vehicles on tree trunks or with 2 wheels or with 4 wheels, etc.

So - in 2020 - **using the formula ASC is very very mismatching with the knowledge developed about consciousness.**

The bicameral mind

Consciousness is “... *the difference between what others see of us and our sense of our inner selves and the deep feelings that sustain it. ... Men have been conscious of the problem of consciousness almost since consciousness began.*” in Jaynes OCBBM

Consciousness is “ *the human ability to introspect* ”.^[5]

Abandoning the assumption that consciousness is innate, Jaynes explains it instead as a learned behavior that “*arises ... from language, and specifically from metaphor.*”^[4]

With this understanding, Jaynes then demonstrated that ancient texts and archeology can reveal a history of human mentality alongside the histories of other cultural products.

His analysis of the evidence led him not only to place the origin of consciousness during the **2nd millennium BCE** but also to hypothesize the existence of an older non-conscious “*mentality that he called the **bicameral mind**, referring to the brain’s two hemispheres*”.^[6] in Wikipedia [Julian Jaynes article](#)

Bicameral mind
no word for « body » nor « thinking »
Xenophany makes the decision

Word for body and thinking
Consciousness of a « self »

Jaynes observes that in the Iliad - told by the first Homer - there is no word for the whole body nor a word for what we call « thinking » i.e. 2.8 thousand years ago Claude has no self, no consciousness.

The ability to make a peephole and to see one’s self, other’s self, etc. was developed shortly after the time of the Iliad.

In the Odyssey - told by the second Homer - Claude has a self, etc..

% of consciousness versus % of xenophany

Many researchers question :

« *Is consciousness just a small island in an ocean of xenophany ?* »

Of course they say « hallucinations » and not yet « xenophany ».

Original state of fullness OSF
with xenophany

Before

After

Before : mankind is in an original state of fullness OSF.

We have seen that Julian Jaynes calls it the bicameral mind.

The life of Claude - 100 thousand years ago - is driven by xenophany.

Julian Jaynes explains how xenophanies were rich of the voices of the bosses and lead to the invention of burials and the invention of gods.

Claude has no need of a consciousness to live his bicameral life.

Claude can build pyramids without consciousness !!!

Original state of fullness OSF
with xenophany

Personal
xenophany

ex : the lonesome
sailor

Before

After

Now - 2020 - we have consciousness.

Does it mean that our bicameral mind, our OSF has disappeared ?

No it is just in the depth of our mind and ready to be active.

Xenophany appear in a large number of situations.

We were interested by the description of xenophanies made by lonesome sailors (1)

Original state of fullness OSF
with xenophany

Before

Personal
xenophany
ex : the lonesome
sailor

Modern
consciousness

Collective
xenophany
ex 1 : fanaticisms
ex 2 : consumerism

After

The bicameral mind with its capacity of fascination/xenophany is the engine behind all sorts of fanaticism.

The fanaticism with belongings as the new god is called consumerism.

A bicameral Claude with OSF Original state of fullness and xenophany

We may say a little more.

Illustration : In Turkey, a monument about the Iliad = the War of Troy

Julian Jaynes observes in the Iliad text the very few number of activities of the Greeks :

- fight against the enemy
- have disputes within ones own tribe
- dine
- talk with a god - xenophany

There is no introspection, no deliberation : a decision is always the fact of a god = a voice or a sign within a xenophany.

And this bicameral mind is still in our brain.

If we compare our ancient brain to a computer our more recent brain has only some additive « apps ».

Part of these « add-ons » are wired in the hardware of our brain i.e. genetically transmitted.

But the story of « wild childs » - grown by animals, etc. - shows that **consciousness has to be taught** to the young Claude.

Four paradigms for an order of things ; paradigms with adoricism, exorcism, passive Claudes and active Claudes

This model was transmitted to me by a shaman/master of the ritual.

From the hunter gatherer original shaman to the large town priest there are 4 steps, 4 paradigms with unique characteristics.

	Management process	Claude's behavior
Original shamanism	adoricism = adding	active
Original devider/witch	exorcism = take of	passive
Master of the ritual	adoricism	active
Priest	exorcism	passive

Illustration : the 4 paradigms and their evolution in time

In 1973, the movie « *The exorcist* » made me laugh and laugh. But ... we can take it as a didactic item.

The story says : 12-year-old Regan McNeil is possessed by the Devil. The exorcist is asked to take the Devil out of Regan's brain and body. In the movie we have the characteristics of the priest paradigm :

- what is inside Claude/Regan is evil
- it has to be taken out of Claude
- Claude is passive in the process

From that we can infer the 3 other paradigms.

A divider/witch (Harry Potters paradigm) would :

- exorcise = extract what is inside Claude
- let Claude be active in the process

A master of the ritual would :

- adorcise = tame or control the evil spirit inside Claude
- not involve Claude in the process = Claude is passive

Most of the healers who are now called « shamans » are in fact « masters of the ritual »
i.e. Claude is passive during the cure.

An original shaman would :

- adorcise = work on what was done wrong with the spirits in general.
Helping spirits come from the otherworld to Claude or Claude travels to the otherworld
- give directions to Claude who is active in the cure

Perspective

These words and diagrams really help me understand spiritual healing situations.

When I exchange with practitioners or researchers - who are seeking for an improvement of their understanding - these words and diagrams help them - so they say.

This doesn't mean they can use the words and diagrams in their papers or dissertations.

Recently that was the case with a brilliant student.

She was working on her dissertation.

She was interested by my proposal but was conscious it would be impossible to **go against the vocabulary of the jury.**

May be she can use it when she be a teacher.

Documents

Wenge Huang (2020) Altered States of Consciousness and the Science behind Buddhism: A Story about Perception

Other papers by Wenge Huang.

<https://worldcrunch.com/tech-science/seeing-things-at-sea-when-solo-round-the-world-sailors-start-to-hallucinate/vend-e-globe-skipper-race-sailing-yacht/c4s10380>

Jaynes, Julian (2000) [1976]. *The Origin of Consciousness in the Breakdown of the Bicameral Mind*(PDF) OCBBM . Houghton Mifflin. ISBN 0-618-05707-2.

4 Jones, William Thomas (1979) Mr. Jaynes and the bicameral mind: a case study in the sociology of belief. Humanities Working Paper, 23. California Institute of Technology, Pasadena, CA. <https://resolver.caltech.edu/CaltechAUTHORS:20090714-105138181>

5 Kuijsten, Marcel (2016). "Introduction". In Kuijsten, Marcel (ed.). Gods, Voices and the Bicameral Mind: The Theories of Julian Jaynes (First ed.). Henderson NV: Julian Jaynes Society. ISBN 978-0-9790744-3-1.

6 Kuijsten, Marcel (2006). "Introduction". In Kuijsten, Marcel (ed.). *Reflections on the Dawn of Consciousness: Julian Jaynes's Bicameral Mind Theory Revisited* (First ed.). Henderson NV: Julian Jaynes Society. ISBN 978-0-9790744-0-0.

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Credit for pictures

https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Iliad_and_Odyssey_monument_5.jpg

[https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Tricycle_2_\(PSF\).png](https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Tricycle_2_(PSF).png)